

Experimental study of extraction behaviour of 2,3-butanediol from aqueous solution with 3-methyl-1-butanol in presence of KCl at 303.15 K

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Abstract : The influence of a solid salt on liquid-liquid equilibrium cannot be ignored because it significantly changes the equilibrium composition. Liquid-liquid equilibrium is the result of intermolecular forces which can significantly change due to salt addition which introduces ionic forces affecting the thermodynamic equilibrium. Aqueous electrolyte liquid-liquid equilibrium is often related to extraction processes. In the present work the salt effect on the system namely water + 2,3-butanediol + 3-methyl-1-butanol has been studied at 303.15 K. The salt used in the above system is KCl with 10% and 15% and 20% concentration. The mutual solubility curve, tie-line data, distribution coefficient and selectivity were determined experimentally at different salt concentrations. The result obtained showed that the salt KCl significantly affect the solubility of 2,3-butanediol in organic solvent. KCl also changes the distribution coefficients and selectivity of 2,3-butanediol by changing the equilibrium composition. The heterogeneity region also increased as compared to the same system without salt. The thermodynamic consistency of the equilibrium tie-line data was ascertained by Othmer-Tobias plot, Setschenow equation and Hand equation.

Keywords : Liquid-liquid equilibria, 2,3-butanediol, salt effect, Othmer-Tobias correlation equation, Hands correlation, Setschenow equation.

Introduction

2,3-Butanediol is a chemical compound of increasing interest due to its potential applications in many industrial fields^{1,2}. It is an important starting material to synthesis methyl ethyl ketone and 1,3-butadiene³. It can be synthesized biotechnologically by fermentation of sugars. The efficient separation of butanediol from dilute solutions resulting from fermentation processes is very important and many solvents have been tested to improve its separation as demonstrated by various authors⁴⁻¹⁰. The extractive recovery of butanediol by selective solvent systems from aqueous solutions, such as fermentation broth has received increasing interest. Liquid-liquid equilibrium data for water + 2,3-butanediol + solvents was investigated in our previous work¹¹.

The presence of dissolved salt significantly changes the phase equilibrium behavior of a mixture, this phenomenon is often referred to as salting-in or salting-out effect. It can be used to optimize separation processes such as rectification to shift the azeotropic conditions, extraction to alter the miscibility gaps and also absorp-

tion and fractional crystallization to change the distribution coefficients. During recent years, attempts have been made to generate the reliable as well as reproducible experimental data for the salt containing systems by Azner¹², Edwin and Desai¹³, Govindarjan and Sabarathinam¹⁴, Hasseine¹⁵, Marcilla¹⁶.

In this study, liquid-liquid equilibrium data as well as the mutual solubility data for the ternary systems of water + 2,3-butanediol + 3-methyl-1-butanol were determined in the presence of KCl as electrolytes at 303.15 K in order to study the salting-out effect on the ternary systems used in this experiments. Distribution coefficient and selectivity which are the quantitative index of effectiveness of separation have been computed from the experimental data. The thermodynamic consistency of the tie-line data were correlated with plots demonstrated by Othmer and Tobias¹⁷, Setchenow¹⁸ and Hand¹⁹ correlations.

Experimental

Chemicals :

3-Methyl-1-butanol was of analytical grade and was

used without further purification. 2,3-Butanediol was obtained from Merck with a purity of 98% and used as such. Double distilled water was used throughout the experimental study. Potassium chloride used was of analytical grade.

Procedure :

The mutual solubilities for water + 2,3-butanediol + 3-methyl-1-butanol at temperature of 303.15 K were determined by using cloud point titrator. Extractions were performed by placing 5 ml of a solution containing 3% w/v 2,3-butanediol in water into a sample cell of the cloud point titrator along with 5 ml of solvent. Water was circulated with the aid of peristaltic pump through the water jacket to maintain temperature. The mixture was stirred for 30 min. Thereafter the two layers were separated by centrifugation, and analyzed for 2,3-butanediol concentrations by GLC-PE Model Sigma 3 B equipped with an FID, using a stainless steel column (2.5 m × 1/8 in. O.D.) packed with chromosorb 101 (80/100 mesh) coated with 3% FFAP. The extractions were carried out in triplicate and standard deviation calculated was found to be less than +/- 0.0065 mass fraction of 2,3-butanediol.

Tie lines values in absence of KCl were determined by making mixtures of the three components, water, 2,3-butanediol and 3-methyl-1-butanol whose compositions fell within the two-phase region of the solubility curve. The mixtures of a 3 ml of 2,3-butanediol in water and 3 ml of 3-methyl-1-butanol were taken in sample bottles and stirred for 30 min to reach equilibrium at 303.15 K. The tie lines in presence of salt were determined by same procedure by adding a weighed amount of KCl (10%, 15%, 20%) crystals to the mixture of 2,3-butanediol, water and 2-methyl-1-butanol. After equilibrium the mixtures were separated by centrifugation and the two layers were analyzed for 2,3-butanediol. The complete composition of the conjugated layers was obtained from the binodal curve. The composition determination was accurate to +/-0.0028 mass fraction. KCl was weighed accurately on precision Metler AE 163 analytical balance with an accuracy to +/- 0.0001 g.

Results and discussion

The liquid-liquid equilibrium for the ternary system water + 2,3-butanediol + 3-methyl-1-butanol was ob-

served at atmospheric pressure and at a temperature of 303.15 K. The mutual solubility and tie line data was determined in the presence of KCl at 10%, 15% and 20% concentrations. Tie lines are straight lines that connect the compositions of the two liquid phases in equilibrium. They are useful in determining the distribution of the solute between two phases, the amount of solvent required for extraction and the number of equilibrium units required. The equilibrium data and mutual solubility data of the system with and without KCl in mass fraction, is given in Table 1 and Table 2 respectively. Ternary equilibrium data with and without KCl was plotted on ternary

Table 1. Equilibrium data for the water (1) + 2,3-butanediol (2) + 3-methyl-1-butanol (3) in presence of KCl for mass fraction w at temperature $T = 303.15$ K

KCl	Water layer			Solvent layer		
	w_{11}	w_{21}	w_{31}	w_{13}	w_{23}	w_{33}
0% KCl	0.950	0.032	0.018	0.090	0.020	0.890
	0.906	0.076	0.018	0.100	0.029	0.871
	0.852	0.128	0.020	0.110	0.040	0.850
	0.830	0.149	0.021	0.120	0.060	0.820
	0.775	0.195	0.030	0.130	0.080	0.790
10% KCl	0.967	0.025	0.008	0.089	0.025	0.886
	0.952	0.041	0.007	0.093	0.051	0.856
	0.929	0.062	0.009	0.098	0.071	0.831
	0.899	0.088	0.013	0.101	0.080	0.819
	0.853	0.130	0.017	0.104	0.082	0.814
15% KCl	0.973	0.022	0.005	0.083	0.030	0.887
	0.954	0.040	0.006	0.088	0.062	0.850
	0.931	0.061	0.008	0.094	0.079	0.827
	0.902	0.087	0.011	0.098	0.085	0.817
	0.869	0.117	0.014	0.101	0.095	0.804
20% KCl	0.976	0.020	0.004	0.077	0.030	0.893
	0.960	0.035	0.005	0.081	0.068	0.851
	0.938	0.055	0.007	0.086	0.080	0.834
	0.909	0.082	0.009	0.092	0.090	0.818
	0.878	0.109	0.013	0.096	0.100	0.804

Table 2. Mutual solubility data for water (1) + 2,3-butanediol (2) + 3-methyl-1-butanol without and in presence of KCl for mass fraction w at temperature $T = 303.15$ K

0% KCl			10% KCl		
w_1	w_3	w_2	w_1	w_3	w_2
0.987	0.013	0.000	0.993	0.007	0.000
0.838	0.022	0.140	0.976	0.013	0.011
0.753	0.035	0.212	0.772	0.015	0.213
0.691	0.056	0.252	0.745	0.028	0.227
0.600	0.108	0.292	0.642	0.059	0.299

Table-2 (contd.)

0.548	0.158	0.294	0.612	0.087	0.301
0.456	0.252	0.292	0.519	0.167	0.314
0.339	0.379	0.282	0.421	0.273	0.306
0.244	0.535	0.221	0.347	0.364	0.289
0.188	0.650	0.162	0.240	0.519	0.241
0.133	0.801	0.066	0.161	0.742	0.097
0.094	0.906	0.000	0.098	0.902	0.000
15% KCl			20% KCl		
0.995	0.005	0.000	0.997	0.003	0.000
0.971	0.012	0.017	0.967	0.014	0.019
0.764	0.015	0.221	0.729	0.019	0.252
0.705	0.024	0.271	0.673	0.027	0.300
0.646	0.051	0.303	0.622	0.054	0.324
0.603	0.082	0.315	0.590	0.089	0.321
0.515	0.161	0.324	0.488	0.167	0.345
0.440	0.240	0.320	0.383	0.283	0.334
0.348	0.341	0.311	0.336	0.343	0.321
0.230	0.536	0.234	0.241	0.496	0.263
0.174	0.686	0.140	0.167	0.679	0.154
0.099	0.901	0.000	0.079	0.921	0.000

diagram and is shown in Fig. 1. It has been seen from the figure that the addition of KCl accelerate the distribution in favour of 3-methyl-1-butanol layer especially above 15% KCl concentration. The solubility of 3-methyl-1-butanol decreases in presence of the salt and increases the

heterogeneous zone of the system. In the present system, it was seen that the areas of solubility curve are more in case of salt addition than that of without salt, similar results were obtained by other authors using same salt but different ternary systems²⁰⁻²². More 2,3-butanediol is shifted towards the 3-methyl-1-butanol phase with increasing salt concentrations. This shifting increases with salt concentration and are maximum at salt saturation.

In solvent extraction processes the solubility of extracting phase in water is often great enough to make it necessary to remove and or recover residual solvent from the aqueous phase leaving the extractor. This is very important to prevent contamination of the products and to permit reuse of the extracting solvent. The effect of KCl addition to the aqueous phase on the solvent solubility in the aqueous phase shows that a great reduction in solvent loss, up to 56%, 72% and 78% can be achieved by adding 10%, 15% and 20% respectively KCl to the system.

Determination of distribution coefficient requires the establishment of equilibrium between water and solvent. This partitioning coefficient can be considered as an important physicochemical parameter for characterizing the lipophilicity and hydrophobicity of a compound. It has been found that KCl has positive effect on the distribu-

Fig. 1. Ternary diagram for experimental LLE of water (1) + 2,3-butanediol (2) + 3-methyl-1-butanol (3) with and without KCl, 0% KCl (■), 10% KCl (▲), 15% KCl (×), 20% KCl (○) at 303.15 K.

tion of 2,3-butanediol between solvent and aqueous phases. Adding 10% KCl leads to an average enhancement of about 131% in distribution coefficient, and reaches to about 224% by adding 20% of this salt. Similar findings were made by Javad and Mahdi²¹ while using water + 2-methylpropanoic acid + (1-methylethyl)-benzene system in presence of KCl. The results obtained are much higher than that obtained by Santos, dAvila and Aznar²² while studying effect of KBr on water + ethanol + 1-pentanol system.

increase in the solubility of 2,3-butanediol in solvent phase. At 5% 2,3-butanediol concentration in presence of 10% KCl concentration there is 2.5 fold rise in separation factor, whereas with 20% KCl concentration there is 3 fold rise in separation factor. A decrease in the distribution coefficient of water is also responsible for higher selectivity in extraction system with salt. The lower distribution coefficient of water can be attributed to the association of the water molecules with un-extracted salt in the aqueous phase, which prevents a transfer of water to the

Fig. 2. Distribution of 2,3-butanediol between water and 3-methyl-1-butanol.

With increase in the KCl concentration, the position of the equilibrium distribution curves shifted slightly towards solvent phase and 2,3-butanediol prefers the solvent phase. But at the same time the effect of KCl had found to decrease with increase in the 2,3-butanediol concentration, i.e. at higher 2,3-butanediol concentration the distribution curve shifts towards the aqueous phase. The equilibrium distribution curve was obtained by plotting mass fraction of 2,3-butanediol in solvent phase (w_{23}) against mass fraction of 2,3-butanediol in aqueous phase (w_{21}) on salt free basis and is depicted in Fig. 2.

Separation factor, which is the measure of the ability of the solvent to remove solute preferentially over water, was significantly affected by the presence of KCl in the system. Effect of KCl concentration on separation factor is shown in Fig. 3. It can be observed that there is a marked increase in separation factor for 2,3-butanediol with increasing concentration of KCl in the aqueous phase²³. This increase in separation factor is due to the

organic phase. This result in higher selectivity which finally will require fewer extraction stages for good separation.

Selectivity graph was constructed by plotting $w_{21}/(w_{21} + w_{11})$ against $w_{23}/(w_{23} + w_{13})$ both on solvent free basis with or without salts is shown in Fig. 4, which reveals that 20% salt solution shows the highest selectivity and the lowest one is without salt system.

The reliability of experimental tie line data was evaluated by means of Othmer-Tobias correlation as shown in eq. (1)

$$\ln [(1 - w_{33})/w_{33}] = a + b \ln [(1 - w_{11})/w_{11}] \quad (1)$$

where a and b are constant.

A plot of $\ln [(1 - w_{33})/w_{33}]$ vs $\ln [(1 - w_{11})/w_{11}]$ for given ternary system on mass fraction and salt free basis is depicted in Fig. 5. The parameters of Othmer-Tobias correlations for tie lines in different KCl concentrations are given in Table 3. As it can be seen, there is a linearity

Fig. 3. Plot of $\ln [w_{21}/(w_{21})_s]$ vs w_{s1} .

Fig. 4. Selectivity curve for water + 2,3-butanediol + 3-methyl-1-butanol ternary system with and without KCl.

Fig. 5. Othmer-Tobias plot at different KCl concentration at 303.15 K.

of the plot and the correlation R^2 approximate near to 1 indicating the consistency of the experimental data.

Setchenow has proposed the following empirical equation eq. (2), for the salt effect on the distribution of solute

	Othmer-Tobias Constants			Hands constants		
	a	b	R^2	$\ln A$	B	R^2
0% KCl	-2.293	0.193	0.999	-1.8116	0.165	0.9983
10% KCl	-2.109	0.142	0.894	-1.566	0.132	0.8185
15% KCl	-2.114	0.154	0.896	-1.4798	0.1241	0.8168
20% KCl	-2.177	0.166	0.898	-1.473	0.1276	0.7984

between the relatively insatiable systems, where K_s is a salt parameter.

$$\ln [(w_{21}/(w_{21})_s)] = K_s w_{s1} \quad (2)$$

Hand's equation eq. (3), for no salt condition is

$$\ln (w_{23}/w_{33}) = B \ln (w_{21}/w_{11}) + \ln A \quad (3)$$

where w_{21} is mass fraction of 2,3-butanediol in aqueous phase, w_{s1} concentration of salt in aqueous phase, w_{11} mass fraction of water in aqueous phase, w_{23} mass fraction of 2,3-butanediol in solvent phase, w_{33} mass fraction of solvent in solvent phase, $\ln A$ and B are constants in Hand's equation. The present system is correlated by using Setschenow and Hands equations.

The salting out parameter K_s for the water + 2,3-butanediol + 3-methyl-1-butanol in presence of KCl is found by a graph of $\ln [w_{21}/(w_{21})_s]$ plotted against w_{s1} and is shown in Fig. 3. Salting out parameter was found to be 0.154. It can be seen that the Setschenow equation fits the data well above 15 wt% ($\approx 2.56 M$) KCl. Similar observations were made by Veera *et al.*²⁴ while studying water + acetic acid + benzene ternary system in presence of CaCl_2 . The Setschenow equation is generally valid for salt concentrations as high as 2 or 3 M, although it fails in dilute conditions Eisen and Joffe²⁵. The deviation can be explained in terms of the hydration theory (Long and Mc Devit²⁶). There will be a certain minimum concentration above which the salting effect will be pronounced. The Setschenow equation is generally valid above this minimum salt concentration.

The equilibrium data (without salt and at different salt concentrations) was simultaneously regressed by using Hands correlations to obtain values for the constants $\ln A$ and B . The results of Table 3 show close values for the constants, suggesting that they are not dependent on the salt concentrations. Thus a good representation of the experimental data is possible using the same set of constants for all the equilibrium data of the system.

Conclusion

The liquid-liquid equilibria of water + 2,3-butanediol + 3-methyl-1-butanol was investigated with and without KCl. The salting out effect of KCl on at three different concentrations of 10%, 15% and 2% NaCl at 303.15 K was studied. The extractive efficiency of 3-methyl-1-butanol for 2,3-butanediol can be considerably enhanced with the addition of KCl into the solvent mixture. An average enhancement in distribution coefficient of 131% and 224% was achieved by addition of 10% and 20% KCl respectively. There was 2.5 fold increase in separation factor with 10% KCl which was found to increase to 3 fold with 20% KCl addition. The solubility of solvent in aqueous phase was found to be greatly reduced to 78% with 20% KCl which decreases the loss of solvent during extraction. The reliability of experimentally measured tie-line data is correlated by Othmer-Tobias equation and the correlation factor R^2 approximate to 1 indicating the consistency of the experimental data. The present system is correlated satisfactorily by using Setschenow and Hands equations. Salting out parameter was found to be 0.154.

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